

Perceptions of regular faculty members on the effectiveness of online classes in the COVID-19 situation: Exploring emerging practices at higher education

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ABSTRACT: Purpose: The Covid-19 situation has changed the perceptions and the attitudes of professionals and educationists in the current era. The dynamics and teaching protocols of education have been affected due to Covid-19. The technology is being integrated in the educational institutions of the developed and developing countries for the last few decades. Since the Covid-19 emerged; the demand for the technology has been increased in many of the field especially in education. This situation demanded the regular faculty members who were not trained for online classes to teach using the online platforms for their teaching purposes. The major objective of study was to explore the perceptions of regular faculty members on the effectiveness of online classes in the Covid-19 situation. Methodology: The qualitative research design with a phenomenological approach was used. The population of the study was all the regular faculty members who were teaching on campuses before Covid-19 but after that situation, they went for online classes and sample size was (N=10) faculty members. Convenience sampling was used to choose participants. The semi-structured interviews were conducted and the data was analysed through thematic analysis.

Findings: The findings revealed three major themes: a) Effectiveness of online classes b) Facilitating factors and c) Issues and Challenges. Implications of the study are drawn from results that can be important for the sake of increasing the progress of educational institutes.

Significance: The study will be helpful for other teachers who are engaged in online classes and universities which are offering online courses such as Allama Iqbal open and virtual university. The study recommends that HEC should provide the equipment and training to develop positive attitudes among teachers. Government should take proactive steps in overcoming barriers and challenges faced by faculty members during conducting online classes.

Keywords: Perceptions, Regular Faculty Members, Online Classes, Covid-19 Situation, Emerging Practice

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1. Introduction

Education played a vital role in the civilization of human life so far; it is the foundation of all human ingenuity. Various systems of education continue to alter from time to time in response to the demands and patterns of human life. (Bahasoan et al., 2020). Moreover, the declaration of the COVID-19 pandemic as a disaster, shift to online schooling, and reliance on technology amid national lockdown highlight the significance of Education during emergencies (Jaffar et al., 2023; Landa et al., 2021).

During COVID-19, online schooling was the primary form of instruction, and technology was heavily relied upon. Some universities, including Allama Iqbal and Virtual University, have been offering online classes for several decades. These universities have several teacher training programmes and platforms that are solely used for conducting online classes. Before Covid-19, some universities inculcated online resources like the internet, websites, and methods such as experiential learning, blended learning, and flipped classroom for online teaching. In previous decades, online classes were less considered in emergency circumstances because there was no such pandemic situation that forces teachers to move for online classes. But after the arrival of Covid-19, even though it was also not considered earlier that physical classes will have to shift towards online classes in emergencies. In order to go for the full-fledged transition of online classes' faculty members were not so prepared and trained to teach on online platforms (Sarwar et al., 2020). The current situation of Covid-19 was so demanding and challenging for teachers in which they had to perform a new role in teaching by using online platforms. Tough, regular faculty members tried to teach through online digital platforms but they faced some issues like technological skills, internet connectivity issues, lack of resources, lack of training at higher education (Farooq et al., 2020).

Globally, it has been observed that industrialized nations with more advanced technological systems, such as China, Korea, and France, were able to take advantage from online resources for academic purposes. During COVID-19, online learning had expanded quickly to offer instruction across a variety of platforms and cutting-edge methods including blended learning and flipped classrooms over time (Mercader & Gairín, 2020).

Pakistan is a developing country, the general method of instruction in public and private schools are physical classroom based. Pakistan implemented a crisis policy during the COVID-19 pandemic, which ceased in-person instruction and switched to an online format. As a result, the industry's adoption rate of online education has increased. A new phase of expansion in the online education sector has been brought about by the spread of the Internet. Along with this growth, the online education sector has benefited from new access points, cutting-edge teaching methodologies, and technology advancements. (Chang & Yano, 2020) and (Giannini & Lews, 2020) argue that, in low economic countries like Pakistan, the rate of advancement in the field of online education has been glacial. However, in light of these new and perilous circumstances brought on by COVID19, online learning has become must and a burning desire for both educators and learners. In short, during the pandemic crisis empowerment, online education has supplanted traditional classroom instruction.

Similarly, (Aslam et al., 2021) recommended that, Countries should not rely on a single remote learning channel to reach their entire population. Providing all children with access to the internet and digital technologies is crucial for minimizing learning risks throughout time. This study examined how regular faculty members perceive the effectiveness of online classes during the Covid-19 pandemic and explored emerging practices in higher education. The study will help to provide the Department of Education, and policymakers with context for developing emergency-related material and resources.

Research Objectives

- I. To explore the perceptions of regular faculty members on the effectiveness of online classes in the COVID-19 situation at higher education.
- II. To explore the facilitating factors of effective online classes in the COVID-19 situation at higher education.
- III. To explore the issues and challenges faced by regular faculty members during online classes in the COVID-19 situation at higher education.

Research Questions

- I. What are the perceptions of regular faculty members on the effectiveness of online classes in the COVID-19 situation at higher education?
- II. What are the facilitating factors of effective online classes in the COVID-19 situation at higher education?
- III. What are the issues and challenges faced by regular faculty members during online classes in the COVID-19 situation at higher education?

2. Literature Review

The definition of online education had constantly been changed over time. According to Kentnor (2015) online education is the delivery of content or material with the online medium of instructions (Internet) students get an education at their convenient time and places. Another definition shows that online education is the process in which instructions through the computer, internet, and software are being provided to students from instructors from time to time (Sun and Chen, 2016).

In the education field, a traditional method was used as a medium of teaching for a long time ago but since the inception of Covid-19, the concept of online classes was commenced at the schools and higher education. However, reviewing the existing literature, Andrews (2019) conducted a study on the benefit of traditional versus online classes at higher education. The findings revealed that traditional classes are different from online classes, as traditional classes have their pedagogies, learning environment, and assessment criteria. Whereas online classes have their platform, learning system, and teaching techniques that must be developed to the learner's needs (Baran et al., 2013).

The Covid-19 is an unprecedented, worldwide pandemic that has been compared to Second World War. This outbreak of a lethal epidemic has engulfed and encircled educational institutions in the world (Azzi-Huck et al., 2020). The UNESCO reported that more than 1.4 billion of students have been affected in the schools, colleges, and universities during the Covid-19 pandemic situation in the world. Moreover, the condition of Covid-19 in schools and universities is increasing day by day (McCarthy, 2020). Though the coronavirus-induced lockdown in the world posed insurmountable challenges to the higher educational institutions, yet the active and responsive governments of these countries rose to the occasion by ensuring online means and methods of education (Chang & Yano, 2020).

As for as Pakistan is concerned, the pandemic proved as a fatal and death blow to Pakistan's economic, social and political sectors. Owing to this pandemic, the government

of Pakistan took immediate steps and issued orders for the closure of all the educational institutions across the country. Subsequently, Higher Education Commission (HEC) directed all higher educational institutions to move traditional classes towards online classes'. Afterward, the majority of the universities in Pakistan shifted towards online classes using different online mechanisms. Despite of limited internet access, online classes were being conducted at the public and private universities level (Rehman et al., 2021). In fact, during this pandemic, the higher education system in Pakistan has been transformed from traditional teaching to online teaching. But unfortunately, this online transformation became a massive challenge due to abysmal digital infrastructure and ICT pedagogical support to faculty members (Alkattan et al., 2020). Furthermore, this pandemic created a plethora of problems owing to poor internet connection and paucity of modalities i.e laptops with cameras and heavy data packages (Sharma, 2021). In this manner, the students, especially those belonging to backward areas are confronting overwhelming challenges in the form of poor internet access and turn purchasing gadgets due to lockdown (Anwar et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, developing countries like Pakistan, where the education sector is at great risk, face various issues during the Covid-19 situation. Muzzini and Aparicio (2013) stated that it is impossible to continue the online education system conventionally. Therefore, to increase the literacy rate and avoid such serious situations it needs to expand the role of technology in educational institutions.

Online classes were conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic in higher educational institutions in all over the world. With the increasing use of the internet and Modalities, online education has been imparted with online instructions. Another study Kotua et al. (2015) stated that many universities in Africa conducted online classes. Moreover, the study revealed that online classes were not effective at higher education due to various challenges related to policy, program development, and academic performance. According to Adyinka (2013, as cited in Paschal et al., 2020) affirmed that Nigeria is a very fast-developing country in the world that offered online classes but unfortunately, they were not successful because faculty members were not qualified and trained in technology. Faculty members face challenges that hinder them to conduct online classes. Furthermore, Tarus (2015) stated that internet connectivity and computers are important in online classes. However, in Africa computers and labs are not installed in universities. Nevertheless, Makokha and Musisya (2016) stated that internet facilities, computers and resource availability are the main issues in Africa so Government should cooperate with higher educational institutions.

The effectiveness of online classes depends upon the motivation of faculty members. Windes and Lesht (2014) stated that faculty members who are teaching online classes can have positive experiences of online classes because they know how to adopt technology in the online classes which supports them to teach in a critical situation. However, the Self-efficacy of faculty members doesn't let them give up online teaching before they get the experience of it. Furthermore, some faculty members feel very uncomfortable in online classes to interact with students as compared to face-to-face classes (Horvitz et al., 2015). Covid-19 has affected the overall education system schools, colleges and especially the high part of higher education in Pakistan and other countries like India, Bangladesh and Africa etc. Marcial (2018) conducted the study in the Philippine and the objective of study was to determine teachers' perceptions regarding effective and hindering factors within technology-based learning.

Dhawan (2020) stated in his study that students and teachers face issues associated with the technology such as login with software, low quality of audio and video, errors in downloading lectures and installation issues. We know that technology has created an easy way to get an education at the doorstep through an online medium of instructions. Technology also supports teachers and students in online classes but sometimes it creates a lot of challenges for learners and instructors. Parkes et al. (2014) stated that students in

online classes are unable to use the learning management system properly. Moreover, they were found less prepared for balancing their work and social lives to manage online classes. Song et al. (2004) conducted a study on issues and challenges faced by students at higher education.

Furthermore, the current study used TAM Model to explore perceptions of Faculty Members on effectiveness of online classes. According to Fred Davis (1989), there are two main factors of the TAM Model; Perceived usefulness (PU) is a factor in which a person believes that how technology or system would benefit them in their job performance.

3. Methodology

Research Design

The research design selected for the current study was qualitative in nature with a phenomenology approach. The research design supported the researcher to answer particular research objectives and questions. The purpose of qualitative research was to explore the perceptions of regular faculty members on the effectiveness of online classes whether they were successful or not in the Pakistani context. In the field of research; Qualitative research is considered a useful design for examining the experience and opinion regarding any phenomena (Hall et al., 2016).

Population and Sampling

The population of the study was all the regular faculty members of public and private universities. There were the least public universities. Therefore, ten mix public and private universities were selected for conducting the research study in Karachi South and East. This was a qualitative study, the sample size in the current study consists of (N=10) regular faculty members from public and private universities of Karachi. One (N=1) regular faculty member from each university was selected. The Participant of the study were both five (N=05) male and five (N=05) female faculty members. The selections of the numbers of participants were ten (N=10) participants between 5 and 25 based on suggestions (Creswell et al., 2012). Furthermore, Morse (1994) suggested that there should be at least (N=6) participants but (N=10) participants are acceptable. While conducting semi-structured interviews with 7 participants' saturation in result were repeated. However, to reduce the bias and random errors (N=10) participants were interviewed.

Data Collection and Analysis

The researcher used convenience sampling to collect data because there were some limitations during Covid-19 and seeking other methods of sampling were not possible. In this method participants were readily and easily available. To conclude the on time and fulfilling the ethical's requirements and reliability and validity of the data. Semi-Structured interviews were online conducted to collect the data from faculty members. Bevar (2014)

emphasized that undertaking the semi-structured interview is to explore the most appropriate way to extract contextualize and in-depth data from participants. The data was recorded in audio and video form on zoom with the permission of the participants before interviewing to maintain the validity of the results.

After the completion of the data collection process, the data was transcribed through thematic analysis; initially, the collected data recorded in audio was transcribed in reading shape and it was important to maintain the balance between emotions, feelings, and impressions in the transcript, later on, the transcribed data was used by demoing and then coding, means most important repetitive terms and sentences in the responses of participants. Research created categories of codes like initial codes, focused codes, and then selective codes. Finally, sub-themes and major themes were generated from codes for further more data analysis process. Thematic analysis was followed by the six steps of suggested for qualitative analysis (Braun & Clarke 2006).

Ethical Considerations

Research used some ethical consideration to keep data confidential. Permission from the chairperson of the department was taken. An inform consent was also taken from the regular faculty members which described the objectives and purpose of the study, interview schedule and time. For the sake of confidentiality, Participants were informed that the collected data will be used only for this research study. The participants were given every right to withdraw from the study at any time. The researcher tried to assure true answers through recording of interview to reduce the researchers' bias.

4. Findings

Once all the interviews were conducted subsequently, Participants' responses were transcribed in words, phrases, codes, subthemes, and finally themes by followings the steps of thematic analysis. There were main three objectives in the current study. Resultantly, the following three major themes were extracted from the collected data regarding research objectives and questions.

The first objective was to explore the perceptions of regular faculty members on the effectiveness of online classes in Covid-19 situations at higher education. The findings of current study present positive and negative perceptions of faculty members on the effectiveness of online classes during Covid-19 situations.

Positive Perceptions

The thematic analysis identified some positive perceptions on the effectiveness of online classes from the faculty members' experiences.

Convenience of Online classes

Online classes are ready to lend a hand when there is not any access to carry on education. In covid-19 situation, it provides evidence that online classes are a good source of persisting teaching and learning. The majority of the respondents expressed: Online classes were more convenient because these were helping teachers in the Covid-19 situation as a source of instructions. Moreover, online classes were more comfortable than physical classes.

A few of the respondents stated that:

"Online classes were not as much effective as physical classes in the normal routine but yes of course, in this pandemic there was more need of online classes to continue the teaching and learning process"

These findings are in line with the findings of Gautum (2020) shows that online classes are free from the hectic schedule because these are more convenient and flexible in terms of managing time and conduct sitting at home during these pandemic situations.

Advent of Covid-19 in the shape of online classes

The online education system of developing countries was lower than developed countries. Online classes are new revolution in the field of education. The findings of Scagnoli et al. (2009) revealed that Covid-19 pandemic has provided opportunities to faculty members to use online pedagogical techniques like Mind mapping, adaptive learning, online quizzes, preparing attractive presentations to get benefit from online classes by using technology. One of the interviewees was opinions of:

“I personally believe that online classes made me much more organized and structured rather than physical classes. Moreover, online classes assisted me in the selection of content, Ideas, resources, and teaching tools”.

Considering the opinion of the above participant's one more respondent shared his experience. According to him:

“In my view, online classes are more mechanical and more focused as compared to face-to-face classes that are one very big transaction that came in my thinking about online classes. As an online teacher, I feel more organized when I was teaching through online classes”

The above statements conclude that online classes have much more worth and efficiency in the terms of serving teachers in the process of teaching during this Covid-19 pandemic and it was an advent for the developing countries.

Negative Perceptions

Followings are the few major subthemes related to the negative perceptions about online classes.

Lack of Interaction Between students and teachers in online classes during the online classes, it is hard to engage students with teachers' presence because the interaction is a basic connection between teachings and learning process. The majority of teachers perceived that there was low participation of students due to lack of interaction between students to students and teachers to students during online classes. The majority of the respondents remarked,

A few respondents emphasized:

“There was no interaction between teacher and students due to time limit and no interactive activities were done which gives them chance to communicate and interact with each other in virtual classes.”

The findings found that interaction builds rapport between teacher and students which is most important in online classes but due to internet connectivity and technical issues teachers are unable to take classes properly.

Students Engagement in online classes

It is fact that appropriate response from students has an immense impact on teachers' teaching. One of the respondents emphasized:

“When I was conducting classes, I constantly ask questions from students to be active during online classes but students could not respond at their end owing to their uncooperative attitude which irritates me in teaching.”

Other female participants expressed her view, according to her,

“There is no any response from the students’ side only the teacher is continuously talking. If students’ responses are not much vigorous, I don’t think we would be able to implement any kind of teaching strategy in that way.”

Facilitating Factors

The second objective was to explore the facilitating factors of effective online classes in Covid-19 situation at higher education. Some of the major factors from the collected data are extracted below.

ICT as a facilitating factor in online classes

The data shows technology has assisted teachers as a facilitating tool during the Covid-19 situation.

In addition, another participant shared:

“ICT condition in our university was fine, machinery and connectivity was fine. Currently, the software and programs used that were updated because management tried not to make teachers in trouble during online classes.”

Majority of respondents agreed,

Online platforms that were available have really been facilitating tools. ICT condition was mostly good but sometimes it creates problems. A few of the participants summed up,

“We believe that ICT has contributed a lot in current situation but some time, we found bit issues slow internet speed and buffering in audio and video which irritated us during conducting online classes.”

Administrative Support

The main source of online classes’ is management support that helps staff to proceed towards successful teaching and learning. The findings of current study show that Majority of respondents were opinions of: “University management was supportive and compassionate in facilitating all the times whenever we were facing any problem, there was IT team; they helped us in creating zoom links and polls for classes to mitigate any risk of technological issues.”

In addition, other respondents outlined: “Our management has been very supportive and the IT team provided us 15 days training on how to operate Zoom, LMS software, and upload lectures that developed my skills”.

Finally, another female participant was opinions of

“Our management provided us internet connectivity on subsidized because we have very good provision of bandwidth within the premises of the university and one thing more, they have us own official accounts registered with LMS and Zoom.”

It was found that university management has been extremely active in facilitating faculty throughout the semester and provided a platform to experience the newness of online classes.

Availability of Resources

Online classes are more convenient than physical classes because it needs some supporting factors, material, and resources for conducting the classes. As the majority of respondents were opinions of:

“We believe; resources are the most important factors that lead towards successful online classes. Meanwhile, university management provides us laptops and registered zoom ID to sign in and conduct online classes.”

In addition, one faculty member added:

“Internet facility means Wifi was provided in the premises of university where we can connect for taking classes because we were unable to connect at home due to poor connection of internet.”

Issues and Challenges

The third objective of this study was to explore the issues and challenges faced by faculty members during online classes. Following results were revealed from data.

Technical Issues

The major source of taking online classes is internet connectivity but unfortunately, not every student has good access to the internet due to their financial status and also remote areas. Majority of respondents was opinions of:

“Most of the time, we faced connectivity issues, due to weak signals students' were disconnected many times during online classes and were unable to join classes again. Some students couldn't take online classes on time lack of internet.”

One female respondent summed up,

“Unfortunately, I was unable to instruct the students clearly because the Internet connection was so weak and my voice was not properly audible to them. As a result, my class was wasted in dealing with their problems.”

Nevertheless, the findings show that regular faculty members faced internet problem that caused disengagement of virtual classes.

Lack of ICT Training

Arora et al. (2020) revealed that it is hard for teachers to use a digital tool to teach using a learning management system without additional preparation. One of the respondent remarked,

“I am sincerely speaking that the problem I faced was my own readiness and openness with new technology. Therefore, I struggled hard to deliver lecture and content restructuring due to the lack of ICT skills.”

Another respondent expressed,

“At the very first time operating zoom functions was difficult for me like how to record the lecture and how to mute student because it was my first experience to use the digital platform without training.”

The findings of this study concluded that majority of teachers faced problems due to a lack of ICT training and tools and teachers were unable to control classes because in online classes students were so far skilled as compared to teachers.

Lack of Resources

Most common issues in universities are related to resources such as inadequate Infrastructure, insufficient gadgets, crashing systems, laptop, and computers. Ayebe and Arthur (2017) conducted a study and revealed that resources are a prerequisite for online

which prove unhindered services to teachers and students. But unfortunately, not everyone is stable to have a personal gadget to use for online classes. Majority of the respondents shared that;

“Lack of infrastructure brings many problems related to online classes, seeing that not everyone may have the strong financial status to purchase a laptop or connect with internet at the same time.”

It is fact that to continue online learning students need such resources which help them to perform their tasks. As other participants stated,

“In remote areas, Even students do not have touch mobile for a video call or access online pdf material so how can we motivate them to buy heavy package for long classes of 2 3 hours.”

Time constraints

In this situation, the burden is put on teachers to adapt themselves to new way of teaching. The findings revealed that majority of participants expressed:

“In online classes, it was difficult for us to schedule classes and manage time according to the situation and needs of students because most of the students belong to remote areas where they face electricity and internet connectivity issues.”

One of the respondents shared,

“Virtual classes are not bad but when it comes to time management I literally lack behind it because continuously explaining things are challenging for me due to time-span and content length to be covered.”

A few of the respondents outlined,

“In online classes, half of the time was consumed in ensuring students to log in and enter in the classes and even so listening students' excuses for (Sir apki awaz nh aarhi) voice disconnection due to mute options.”

Power consumption

The majority of respondents shared their responses show that load shedding and electricity failure issues cause extreme worrisome in students and teachers during online classes. One of the respondents shared,

“We are living in a non-standardized country where we face electricity issues on daily basis, so in the covid-19 situation I face power failure issues during conducting online classes.”

Another participant's highlighted,

“In my area, electricity was a big problem; I was not able to schedule my classes due to unconditional failure of electricity.”

A female teacher expressed her views,

“Sab sy bari bat hoti h bajli ki bajli hogi tu class lengy na (If there would be the provision of electricity, then we would be able to conduct online classes).”

This theme highlighted the most important issues which are faced by the faculty members in teaching online classes. Moreover, it revealed that without electricity classes' couldn't be conducted on time.

5. Discussion

The findings of current study revealed that majority of the respondents' perceived, online classes can't be compared with physical classes. However, they stated that online classes were more convenient to conduct at home rather than going to university on a daily basis because less time is consumed. The findings of Saykili (2019) also concluded that online classes are more convenient and effective in providing deep learning which can be developed by integrating the digital and virtual approaches. Moreover, Adler (2001) supported the above statement that online classes are most convenient and flexible for those students and teachers who live in a faraway location. It is common fact that in the current situation virtual classes lend a hand between teachers and students. Moreover, the findings of this study revealed that teachers face different issues but technology constantly supported them. Technology as a facilitating tool has gone beyond the level and served teachers as a need in online classes during the covid-19 pandemic. Roy (2019) stated that technology helps teachers to interact with students and increase the learning and teaching process with online resources. Reviewing the literature, it was found that this statement is in line with findings of a study conducted in Philippine Marcial by morsel et al. (2020) the use of technology can make an easy process for teachers who are engaged in teaching online classes. Furthermore, the findings of current study revealed that faculty members faced some problems associated with technical issues, lack of resources, power consumption and time constrains during conducting online classes. A study conducted by Kahu et al. (2014) revealed that most of faculty members have specialized internet issues in taking online classes. Another study conducted by Dzakiria (2012) argued that online classes were difficult to conduct because it needs appropriate technical support for teaching and learning but every faculty member and student do not have the same financial status to pay money for heavy internet and digital modalities.

6. Conclusion

The results and findings of the study concluded that online classes are effective and convenient at their own pace but online classes can't be compared with physical classes because teachers are not able to interact with students and give activity-based tasks in online classes. In online classes' activities such as debate and discussion, jigsaw techniques and cooperative learning activities could not take place during teaching controversial issues. Online classes can't replace the physical classes but these are only used as a temporary solution to avoid the wasting of students' time. Some faculty members showed their positive perceptions on the effectiveness of online classes that online classes are convenient and flexible in the means of time saving. They stated that covid-19 has provided this opportunity and an advent in the shape of online classes. On the other side, a few faculty members expressed negative perceptions such as lack of interaction, students' engagement and unfavorable learning environment disturbed the educational environment. Furthermore, some facilitating factors supported faculty members in conducting online classes such as administrative support, ICT Support and resources provided by the universities. In the process of conducting online classes, some issues and challenges were found such as internet connectivity, power consumption, low-quality equipment, and teaching complexity due to the lack of teachers' ICT training. Although universities have made efforts in order to solve these problems and improve the way of online classes. However, technical issues are still the most difficult to solve due to the capacity of the

services owned by the management of higher educational institutions. Nonetheless, universities have to create programs to meet these issues especially for students and teachers of rural areas or low-income families.

7. Recommendations

Online education has gained an immense attention for the continuation of teaching and learning during the Covid-19 because it has provided support to fulfill the students' needs. However, it is recommended that

1. Management of universities should provide equipment such as laptops and internet devices to students and teachers from university the funds those are not able to afford and live in remote areas.
2. Policymakers must frame teachers' technical based trainings program on online teaching as faculty members can enhance advanced technological skills.
3. Higher Education Commission should make strong plans in order to develop positive attitudes among teachers and students towards virtual teaching and learning.
4. Stakeholders should ensure the cybercrime and fiber security issues in online classes to protect the personal data of teachers and students.

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